

Kinetic study of specific base catalyzed hydrolysis of ethyl caprylate in water-DMSO binary system

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Kinetic study of the hydroxide anion catalyzed hydrolysis of ethyl caprylate has been done in water-DMSO binary system at various composition (10–60%, v/v) of DMSO and at 20–35°. Specific rate constant values increase with increasing proportion of DMSO at all temperatures. Increase in specific rate constant value with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium supports Parker's view. A reasonable interpretation of variations in specific rate constants and thermodynamic parameters have been put forward on the basis of solute-solvent interaction, solvation of the transition state and bulk dielectric constant of the medium.

Study of the effect of dipolar water-miscible aprotic solvents on the hydrolysis of esters and amides has been reported by a number workers¹. But there is no uniformity in the explanation put forward to explain experimental results. Ester hydrolysis is an ion-dipole type of reaction and assuming the predominance of electrostatic effects, Ingold² as well as Laidler⁶ have predicted a decrease in rate with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. The predictions of Ingold and Laidler have been supported by numerous works⁴. However, on the basis of solvation phenomenon Parker⁵ predicted increase in rate in case of ester hydrolysis of dipolar aprotic solvent like DMSO. This contention has been supported by numerous experimental works^{6,7}. Therefore, more work is needed to be done to establish the mechanism of solvation and the effect of dielectric constant of the medium. Though works on lower acid esters have been reported, hydrolysis of esters of higher fatty acid like caproic acid has not been studied, hence the present work was undertaken. It was also proposed to explain variation in specific rate constant in terms of thermodynamic activation parameters.

Results and Discussion

The specific rate constants of hydroxide anion catalyzed hydrolysis of ethyl caprylate calculated in different percentage composition of water-DMSO binary solvent mixture at temperatures 20, 25, 30 and 35° are shown in Table 1.

A perusal of the above table reveals that the rate constant values are gradually increasing with the gradual addition of DMSO in the reaction medium at all the temperatures of study. The trend of change in *k* values is thus just opposite to the results of some workers^{6,8} who studied hy-

Table 1. Specific rate constant ($k \times 10 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) at different temperatures

%DMSO (v/v)	20°		25°		30°		35°	
	<i>k</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>D</i>
10	4.65	79.91	7.26	78.05	11.83	76.32	18.38	74.63
20	5.49	79.62	8.04	77.74	13.07	75.99	19.56	74.28
30	6.25	79.04	9.49	77.12	14.27	75.38	20.93	73.70
40	7.18	78.03	10.40	76.11	15.41	74.38	22.76	72.71
50	8.40	76.41	12.23	74.55	18.51	72.38	24.95	71.25
60	9.64	73.92	14.05	72.25	19.85	70.68	27.24	69.14

drolysis of esters in aqua-DMSO mixtures. Our results fall in line with the theory put forward by Parker⁵, according to which 'rate of such reactions in which the transition state passes through large polarization should be faster in aprotic solvents than in protic solvents'.

A review of literature on variation of rate constant values with changing composition of aqua-organic solvent systems reveals that two factors are mainly responsible for variation in rate constant values : (i) solvent-solute interactions and (ii) bulk dielectric constant of the reaction medium. As the dielectric constant of DMSO is less than that of water (at 25°, $D_{\text{DMSO}} = 46.6$, $D_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 78.3$), the bulk dielectric constant of the medium gradually decreases with increasing proportion of DMSO in the reaction medium. Had dielectric constant factor been the deciding factor in influencing the rate, *k* values should have decreased with increasing proportion of DMSO and decreasing value of bulk dielectric constant of the medium. In our study, the solute-solvent interaction appears to be the more probable factor influencing the rate, dielectric constant factor being only a secondary and less influencing factor. Aqua-DMSO medium has been

termed as TNAN (Typical Non Aqueous Negative) type of binary mixture⁹.

Table 2 Values of E_c , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger , and $-\Delta S^\ddagger$ in different solvent mixtures

%DMSO (v/v)	E_c kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	At 25°	
			ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
10	71.80	67.81	73.79	20.07
20	65.81	63.82	73.53	32.59
30	62.82	60.35	73.12	42.85
40	56.84	57.44	72.90	51.89
50	53.18	52.82	72.16	66.04
60	52.90	51.55	72.16	69.15

Intermolecular association of this solvent occurs in such type of binary mixtures. Parker and Tomilison¹⁰ pointed out the breakdown of water-water interaction by adding DMSO as a co-solvent in it. This solvent-sheath breaking nature of DMSO has differential effect on solvation of initial state and of transition state. The rate constant will naturally be affected by such specific solvation changes. As DMSO is a poor anion solvater there will be decrease in solvation sheath of the anion, OH⁻ (reactant) with gradual increase in DMSO proportion in the reaction medium. Obviously, the reactant anion (OH⁻) will gradually become more and more free and labile for attack on the ester causing its hydrolysis. On the other hand, the transition state though having negative charge on it, is quite large in size and so will be little affected (in respect of solvation) by gradual increase in DMSO in the reaction medium. Thus our study points to the nature of solvation model presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

The net result will be that there will be gradual increase in rate and gradual decrease in activation energy with successive increase in DMSO proportion in the aqua-organic solvent system. Thermodynamic activation parameters have been recorded in the Table 2. The trend of change of E_c , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔG^\ddagger , and $-\Delta S^\ddagger$ values supports our view of more desolvation of initial state as compared to transition state.

The effect of variation of ionic strength of medium on rate constant values is negligibly small. This suggests that the solvolysis reaction under study is of ion-dipole type and not of ion-ion type.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR/standard grade (B.D.H. or E. Merck). DMSO was purified by reported method¹¹. Double-distilled water from alkaline MMnO₄ solution was used for preparing different solutions used in experiment. Ethyl caprylate was purified by usual fractional distillation process. The ester solution in DMSO-water mixture of known composition and standard aqueous alkali solution were thermostated for 0.5 h in a bath controlled within $\pm 0.5^\circ$. The two solutions were then mixed so that the reaction started. Aliquots (5 ml) of the mixture were removed from the reaction mixture at different intervals of time, mixed with standard HCl solution (5 ml) and finally back-titrated with standard baryta solution. Reproducible results were obtained.

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